

INFLUENCE OF CNT MODIFICATION ON THE FATIGUE LIFE OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The influence of CNT modifications of the matrix on the fatigue life of glass-fibre epoxy hybrid composites was investigated. It was found that the CNT have a positive influence on fatigue life. In addition, there is a potential of the hybrid composites to act as self-sensing material for damage monitoring in fibre reinforced composite structures.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, fatigue, damage sensing, electrical conductivity, smart materials

Introduction

Glass fibre reinforced polymers (GFRPs) are an important group of materials in lightweight constructions. Most of the parts produced from FRPs, like aircraft wings or wind energy turbine blades are designed for high load levels and a lifetime of 25 years or more, leading to an extremely high number of load cycles to sustain. Especially a typical wind turbine rotor has a rotational speed of around 20 1/min. This leads to 28.000 load cycles per day under alternating load, due to the self-weight of the structure. Estimating a lifetime of 25 years, the structure has to survive $3 \cdot 10^8$ cycles during service life. Consequently, the fatigue life and the degradation of the mechanical properties are aspects to be considered. Therefore, improving the fatigue properties of FRP-structures has gained importance. A number of studies is reporting improvements in static mechanical properties of composite materials modified with different nanoparticles [e.g. 1-2], but there is only one publication on the influence of nanoparticles on the fatigue life of composites under mechanical load [3].

This work reports on composite materials with CNT modified matrices tested under tensile, compressive and alternating fatigue loading. The modification of the epoxy matrix with different nanoparticles leads to a significant increase in inter-fibre fracture strengths, which shifts the first-ply failure to higher values and thus might increase fatigue life .

Materials

Glass fibre reinforced polymers were produced with a low temperature curing Epoxy system RIM 135 and the amine hardener RIMH 137, supplied by MGS Hexion, glass fibre non crimp fabrics GF-NCF from Saertex Wagener and CNT as nanoscaled filler. The epoxy system and the non crimp fabrics are common materials in the RTM manufacturing of wind turbine rotor blades. For the fatigue tests quadraxial coupons were produced with the fibre orientation $[0_{49}, 45_{23}, 90_5, -45_{23}]$.

As nanoscopic filler, high aspect multi wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) type C100 from Arkema, exhibiting diameters between 10-30 nm were blended into the resin with a high-shear mixing process [2]. Reference laminates without CNT modification were also produced for comparison.

The CNT modified epoxy resin exhibited filler contents above the electrical percolation threshold (0.3 wt.%). A filler concentration of 0.3 wt% in the matrix results to around 0,1 wt% in the composite with 50% fibre volume of glass fibres. The specific electrical conductivity of the hybrid composite ranged from 10^{-4} S/m to some 10^{-2} S/m.

Materials processing and specimen preparation

The CNT fillers were mixed into the neat epoxy resin using a three roll mill, described in detail in [4]. After adding the hardener the mixture was blended in a vacuum stirrer to degas volatile constituents like moisture or solvent residues, in order to avoid the inclusion of air bubbles, and to apply shear to the mixture. Composites were produced in an RTM process. For the fatigue tests coupons were produced with two layers of the $[0_{49}, 45_{23}, 90_5, -45_{23}]$ NCF, to achieve a $[0, 45, 90, -45, 45, 90, -45, 0]$ - lay-up. The laminates produced had a fibre volume fraction of about 40%. After the RTM process the composites were cured for 24h at RT and after 50mm GFRP-strips as end-tabs were applied and specimens according to DIN EN ISO 527-4 with the dimensions 25 x 3 x 250 mm were cut and edge-polished, the coupons were post-cured (according to the recommendation of the resin manufacturer) at 80°C for 15 hours. Finally, conductive silver paint was used for contacting the electrically conductive coupons for in situ resistance measurements.

Experimental

Fatigue tests were performed in 3 different load regimes on a Instron/Schenk servohydraulic actuator with a maximum load capacity of 100 kN. The dynamic testing was performed at a frequency of 6 Hz to avoid sample heating. In the tests with partial or fully compressive load cycles, an support was used to prevent buckling of the coupons. The test coupons were fatigue loaded under the load conditions (R= 0.1, tension-tension; R= -1, tension-compression; and R= 10, compression-compression) with a constant stress amplitude until the final failure. Load cycles were counted and plotted in an S-N-curves.

The DC-electrical resistance variation of the composites were measured using a Keithley 2602 source. Resistance measurements with a sampling rate up to 50 measurements per second were possible with this setup, allowing a precise measurement of electrical resistance of a fatigue loaded coupon.

Results & Discussion

In Figure 1 is shown the S-N curve resulting from a fatigue test under $R = -1$. The CNT modified composite material shows a significant increase in fatigue life under all load levels compared to the unmodified reference. The fatigue life increased up to a factor 100 at the same stress loading.

figure 1 S-N curve of reference and MWCNT modified GFRP. $R = -1$ (tension-compression)

It can be seen that for high maximum stress values close to the static fracture strength of the laminate, the effect of the CNT modification of the matrix is less pronounced. This is not surprising since for high stress values, failure is a fibre dominated process and improvements of matrix properties have minor influence on fibre dominated static properties. For low stress values in the technically interesting high-cycle fatigue regime the matrix modification with CNT leads to a significantly higher fatigue life at the same stress value. This process is due to the fact that the creation and growth of inter fibre failure, which is the origin of all other damage in a fatigue loaded composites is delayed to higher load levels, respectively higher cycle numbers, by the nanoparticles in the matrix. As a result, specimens live longer under dynamic load and the slope of the S-N curve is significantly less steep.

This can also be observed in figure 2, where the S/N curves under dynamic compressive loads ($R = 10$) are shown. Again, the CNT modified material exhibits a less steep S/N-curve than the unmodified reference material.

figure 2 S-N curve of reference and material modified with MWCNT. R= 10 (compression-compression)

A first approach to explain this phenomenon is the correlation of an increased interfibre fracture strength and fatigue life. For example, the stress to first inter fibre-fracture could be increased by 8-16% for the CNT modified composite materials [??]. Since the damage evolution in fatigue loaded composites has its origin in interfibre -fracture, and the interfibre fracture strength could be increased by the addition of CNT to the matrix, all subsequent damage in the fatigue loaded materials appear at a higher stress values. Thus, the life of a fatigue loaded coupon with a nanomodified matrix is higher than that of the reference composite.

Additionally, for every composite material produced, a correlation between the change in electrical resistance and the state of loading/damage was found. This phenomenon was found to be independent on the type of mechanical test and the direction of the resistivity measurements. An exemplary testing result is given in figure 3, where a test coupon was loaded in tension-tension fatigue with R= 0.1. Stiffness of a coupon under dynamic tensile load and the respective change of the electrical resistance is plotted vs. time. Two main effects can be observed: with the typical stiffness decrease of the composite due to the evolution of micro cracking and inter fibre fracture, a slight increase in electrical resistance can be observed. This is due to an interruption of the electrical conductive pathways in the percolated network formed by the nanoparticles in the matrix. Since it is a stress controlled test, with decreasing stiffness due to damage induced degradation of the test coupons, increases in strain are the consequence with each consecutive load cycle. Previous publications [1] already showed this dependency

of electrical resistance from the strain in tensile tests. The second important observation is, that with the occurrence of pronounced damage in the loaded coupon, parallel to a spontaneous drop in stiffness an increase in electrical resistance occurs. In this case, delamination and rupture of load carrying fibres and rovings were observed. Also, final failure of the material could be detected by detecting the electrical resistance variation.. At rupture of the test coupon under tensile load, all conductive pathways were interrupted and the electrical resistance approaches infinity.

figure 3 Stiffness degradation and el. resistance change at R= 0.1. Resistance measured in thickness direction of the tested coupon [1]

The used setup also allowed sampling of DC electrical resistance with a measurement sampling rate up to 50 digital measurements per second. In figure 4, DC resistance is plotted versus time for one exemplary second in the fatigue life of a specimen. It can be clearly seen that it is possible to fully detect the DC resistance variation evolving from each load cycle. This is due to the elastic response of the nanocomposite network which leads to a change of tunneling resistance, but not to damage of the composite itself.

figure 4 - Resistance of specimen under 6Hz dynamic tensile load (R= 0.1), measurement at sampling rate of 50 1/s

Conclusion

Significant improvements of fatigue life due to the matrix modification with CNT have been achieved. This is valid for tension-tension and compression-compression loading conditions. The reason for the increase in fatigue life lies in the suppressed nucleation and growth of microdamage like inter fibre fracture, which is the initial damage and the origin for all further damage occurring during fatigue life. A delay in the appearance of the damage consequently influences the high cycle fatigue life.

Additionally, the apparent load and damage in fatigue loaded CNT modified matrix polymers can be monitored by measuring the DC resistance due to straining and/or interruption of percolated nanotube networks. A future application of this damage sensing technology in glass fibre reinforced polymers could be found in the field of non-destructive testing, e.g. for the online remote degradation monitoring of composite structures, e.g. wind turbine rotor blades.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), Project 01RI05236, “Higher efficiency of wind energy by using innovative, sensitive structural materials with improved mechanical properties”.

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